

Rethinking Subjectivity and Agency through New Materialism and Performance Art

New materialism(s), a specific domain within posthumanism, developed in opposition to the linguistic turn with the aim to destabilize language as the primary constructor of reality (Alaimo & Hekman, 2008). It has conceptualized the post-humanist approach toward matter based on the large majority of humanist and science studies work. Through the lens of new materialism, matter does not exist with pre-definable properties, or in other words, it “does not refer to an inherent, fixed property of abstract, independently existing objects” (Barad, 2007, p. 151); rather, matter is a group of atoms that momentarily assume the characteristics of entities while waiting for a new relation to form. This kind of dynamic interaction between matters is called as entanglements since there are no distinct, predetermined entities. Thus, all matter, human or non-human, exists in connections with other forms of matter, and boundaries between entities can only be temporarily established. Challenging the passivity of matter by ascribing it agency rejects traditional dichotomous concepts such as human/non-human, discourse/matter, subject/object, mind/body, culture/nature, male/female, etc. (Barad, 2007).

Karen Barad is particularly known for her theory on agential realism, which is extensively discussed in her book *Meeting the Universe Halfway: Quantum Physics and the Entanglement of Matter and Meaning*, as well as in her influential article “Posthumanist Performativity: Toward an Understanding of How Matter Comes to Matter.” As an alternative to representationalist ontologies that divide ‘material’ from ‘semiotic’ reality, Barad proposes agential realism (Barad, 2003). For Barad, the ‘realism’ in agential realism refers to a belief that scientific theories can offer reliable access to the onto-epistemology of the world – that theory can provide reliable access to experiences of becoming (Barad, 2007). What differs radically

from traditional realism, however, is the broad concept of agent, and the notion of intra-action. Realness, in the agential realist sense, does not signify anything fixed, static or prior. Rather, what is real, is processual intra-active entanglements that continually constitute the world. As Barad (2003) noted, "...relata do not pre-exist relations; rather, relata-within-phenomena emerge through specific 'intra-actions', and furthermore, . . .there are no independent relata, only relata-within-relations" (p. 815).

Barad refers to these as 'intra-actions,' rather than 'interactions,' because her argument is that intra-action exists prior to the actual object to which they are linked, and it comes to matter as a result of these intra-actions (Barad, 2007). In other words, interaction conveys a sense of internal change in independent entities with preexisting relata, but intra-action highlights the co-constituting character of different matters in entanglements. As a result, matters emerge within their dynamic of intra-activity.

In the context of intra-action, agency cannot be attributed to objects or subjects, but rather to a number of continual processes within relationships that (re)configure meaning and boundaries, which can then "contest and rework what matters and what is excluded from mattering" (Barad, 2003, p. 827). Benedictus de Spinoza (1996) considers this process as 'modes', which are constituted in accordance with various flaws. Such flaws can be compared to rhythms that effect other bodies along with other things or other rhythms. If one thinks of the body as a collection of rhythms and capabilities that is able to affect as well as be affected, he/she shifts away from more essentializing discourses of subjects and substitutes them with ways of thinking that focus on the relationships of affects and capacities (Atkinson, 2017). According to Deleuze (1988), these modes of thought result in an ethology, which is a study "of capacities for affecting and being affected that characterizes each thing" (p. 125).

It is significant to explore the concept of assemblage in this context since it does not imply the conventional understanding of causality, of causal relationships between humans or humans and non-humans. Causality in the context of intra-activity is not to be understood as an action-response or cause-effect relationship of different entities between and within phenomena (Barad, 2003). Their relationship does not provoke a linear sequence of logically initiated events. Intra-active causality occurs when one or more entities of phenomena create possibilities for other entities of phenomena to get affected in one way or another. Indeed, it is machinic relationships between entities (Atkinson, 2017).

In an assemblage, there is neither a 'subject' nor an 'object' (Anderson, 2010). One could consider assemblage as a 'territories' (Guattari, 1995, p. 28) created and contested by the affects among relations. Thus, an affect is a 'becoming' that reflects a shift in an entity's state or capabilities and results in the development of new affective capacities in assemblages (Deleuze & Guattari, 1988, p. 256). Since a single affect can result in the formation of multiple capacities, social production is 'rhizomic', or a branching flow, rather than linear (Deleuze & Guattari, 1988, p. 7). As a result, there is not a world of distinct entities that interact, instead, a world of different forces co-exist, work and develop together that, consequently, leads to diverse becomings (Atkinson, 2017). According to what Deleuze and Guattari stated (1988), "becoming is not history, history only designates a set of conditions however recent they may be, from which one turns away in order to 'become,' that is, in order to create something new" (p. 231).

A relational becoming known as 'becoming with a world' involves interactions between human and non-human actants. Therefore, the conception of the human subject must incorporate concepts of the non-human and the more-than-human, which means that the process of becoming must be exposed to that which lies outside the human as it is (Atkinson, 2017). Therefore,

subject is not conceived in terms of essentialism, that is, as a separate, autonomous creature living in a distinct objective world (Barad, 2007). The subject is not seen as a duality between the mind and the body. Subjectivity, on the other hand, can be conceived of as a temporal phase made up of various relational processes that take place in and within a world made up of various intensities, ideas, feelings, and actions (Atkinson, 2017).

Ana Mendieta is a performance artist who brought the concepts of ‘becoming with a world’ to life. Mendieta’s works reveal a distinct process of creation that suggests a collaboration between the nature and her body. She was forced to leave Cuba for the United States, thus, she was trying to figure out who she was and where she belonged (Barbour, 2013). Through her performances, Mendieta explored a deep bond between human and non- human life. She expressed her body and linked the body, the earth, and art together as one in a variety of ways and with various natural materials such as mud, sand, rock, water, grass, and fire.

Mendieta *Silueta Series* (1976), as an example, is a ‘becoming-space of time’ that shows her collaboration with the earth through a dynamic of intra-activity. In *Tree of Life* from the *Silueta series*, Mendieta is shown standing nude and upright, covered in mud, and at the base of a large oak tree with her arms lifted on either side of her head in order to build a connection with nature (Best, 2007). Her utilization of her body in configuration with the natural elements of the earth can be seen as presenting an applied co-articulation between human and non-human existence. She becomes part of the bark of the tree, part of the forest, and thus a part of nature. She does not want to be a body in nature as though nature is a container; instead, she tries to be a part of nature in its differential becoming. According to Donna Haraway (1992), bodies are created, rather than born, “in world-changing technoscientific practices by particular collective actors in particular times and places” (p. 297). It means that body, as material-semiotic entities,

develops from particular bodily production apparatuses—that is, configurations of human and non-human beings, discourses, technologies, time, place, space, and other practices.

As Mendieta (2015) stated, “my art is grounded in the belief in one universal energy which runs through everything from insect to man, from man to specter, from specter to plant, from plant to galaxy. My works are the irrigation veins of this universal fluid” (p. 323). In opposition to the concept of dominating nature, Mendieta describes the *Siluetas* as a journey to discover her place, or in other words, her context in nature (Mendieta, 1988). By doing so, Mendieta blurs the boundaries of socially accepted dichotomies and shows that human and nature are not separate entities. Mendieta (1988) stated, “through my earth/body sculptures, I become one with the earth... I become an extension of nature and nature becomes an extension of my body” (p. 71). Thus, Mendieta’s performance demonstrates that all existences are enmeshed within interdependent systems in which there is no ‘self’ and there is no ‘other’, and all entities are in an ongoing and dynamic material-discursive practice of transitioning from one state to another in space and time.

The intra-active dynamic material relationship between Mendieta’s body and nature deconstructs the Western dichotomies and can be considered as a way for both woman and nature to heal from the wounds inflicted by patriarchy’s systemic oppression (Glazebrook, 2002). It refers to the notion that Mendieta must return her body to earth as a method of identifying herself, as well as the idea that she must perceive nature as a living, breathing body. Hence, unlike Western world structures in which woman and nature are considered passive, Mendieta shows how both nature and body are alive, agentive, active, and dynamic participants in the world’s becoming.

Mendieta's identity as an intra-active identity must be accepted along with the fact that knowledge, identity, and bodies all have inherent boundaries (Ødegård, 2018). Mendieta's identity is a process of becoming where one thing becomes another thing. It is an enactment, a doing that does not belong to humans or non-human but appears in their relation. Merleau-Ponty (1968) points out this kind of intertwining and reversible relations as flesh: "There is no limit or boundary between the body and the world since the world is flesh" (p. 138).

The materiality of the body provides a framework for thinking about how relationality and material bodies coexist and are intertwined with one another. This entanglement gives a greater framework for bodies to add meaning to the world rather than having the body be reduced to simply perception. As a result, the body becomes a body through its relational processes, which is networked with the 'lines of forces' existing within and on an axis of becoming. Because of the links with other bodies in the nature, the material reality of the body, which is made up of a single matter substance, further becomes a material reality (Henderson-Espinoza, 2016). Rosi Braidotti (1994) presents this argument when she stated, "clearly for feminist corporeal materialism, the body is not a fixed essence, a natural given... the body as the theoretical topos is an attempt to overcome the classical mind-body dualism of Cartesian origins, in order to think anew about the structure of the thinking subject. The body is then an interface, a threshold, a field of intersecting material and symbolic forces" (p. 169). Such an approach contends that the body serves as a device for undermining the mind-body dichotomy. Such fluid ideas of the body would proceed as follows: How is it possible that there might be some type of absolute and pure barrier between the body and the mind if the body is truly a complicated network of agential forces, not an isolated thing, but a network of overlapping and differential boundaries? (Kaufman, 2022)

Carolee Schneemann is another artist who made these ideas palpable. For Schneemann, the understanding of one's body, physical action, and the intra-action between the body and its environment are all primary concerns. *Up to and Including Her Limits* (1971-76) is one of her performances in which Schneemann hanged a rope and harness above a huge canvas and suspended naked using her body to draw on it. In this performance, Schneemann demonstrates how matter, including things, objects, bodies, spaces, and places participate actively in the world's becoming.

As Schneemann (1959) stated, "I am after the interpenetrations and displacements which occur between various sense stimuli; the interaction and exchange between body and the environment outside it; the body as the environment" (box 2, folder 2.2). The artist, indeed, is simultaneously creating a world and imagining herself to be a part of it. Schneemann experiences a sense of becoming which is determined only through the process of intra-activity between her body and different entities, rather than being found pre-existing in it. To say it in other ways, her body is physically entangled with its discursive production rather than existing prior to it. "On an agential realist account, discursive practices are specific material (re)configurations of the world through which local determinations of boundaries, properties, and meanings are differentially enacted" (Barad, 2003, p. 138). Schneemann's performance is a move away from anthropocentrism since agency is not ascribed to someone or something; instead, all entities (both, animate and inanimate) are important parts of phenomena and have agential capacities that, consequently, contributes to the deconstruction of binary oppositions including, human/non-human, mind/body, and subject/object.

The essence of the human being is much more complex than any static essence. The body is continuously in dynamic relation to a whole since the being of bodies occurs within a single

totality of matter, articulated in many modes. The body is indeed a way to go from being to becoming. Therefore, one must consider his/her identity as a form of relation, which will entail ‘becoming’ (Colebrook, 2000). Gatens (1996) suggests that “[w]e need to understand and remember how we became what we are, not in order to live what we have become as our ‘truth’ but rather as our conditions of possibility for that which we may become” (p. 77). Becoming is neither an arbitrary overlay nor a representation of an innate sexuality; rather, the body “becomes” to allow for “becoming” in general to emerge.

The Artist Is Present, Marina Abramović’s MOMA exhibition, is another example of how the body is a network of discourses and materials, an intra-active becoming that could be different at any moment. During the performance of *The Artist Is Present*, Abramović sat on a chair for more than 700 hours to explore the complex relationship between artist and audience. According to Abramovic, this performance was about being in the present (Abramović, 2010). *The Artist Is Present* encourages audiences to embrace the present moment in spite of experiencing feelings like pain, fear, or discomfort. It shows that there is no experience outside of time and space, while both are themselves variable (Bakhtin, 1981) and the boundary between them is continually being made and remade. Consequently, there may be numerous alternative values, chronotopes, and beliefs derived from intra-active relationality inside any given circumstances.

The performance by Abramovic challenges the audience to consider the actual, material, and ontological aspects of human existence due to its emphasis on the body and embodiment (Richards, 2009). Dostoevsky Bakhtin (1981) acknowledged “the impossibility of solitude, the illusory nature of solitude. The very being of man... is the deepest communion. To be means to communicate... I cannot manage without another; I cannot become myself without another (in

mutual reflection and mutual acceptance)” (p. 287). Bakhtin’s ideas about solitude have taken shape by Abramovic. Abramovic showed how each of the pairs—self and other, artist and audience, human and the non-human—exists in a constantly interdependent intra-action.

Although a body might be thought of as an assemblage of various organs, actions, memories, feelings, and thoughts, there is no definitive meaning that could be identified for the body. The idea of multiplicity offers a chance to give up the notion of an essentialized or unified self and adopt the perspective that what we refer to as an individual is actually a continually changing set of processes that take place on multiple levels (Atkinson, 2017).

New materialists are met with a significant type of epistemological impossibility in their acceptance of the agencies and interdependencies of matter and organisms: the impossibility of fully understanding and predicting complicated causal processes (Frost, 2011). The division between ontology and epistemology is a reflection of a metaphysics that presumes an intrinsic distinction between humans and non-humans, mind and body, subject and object, matter and discourse. However, through the lens of new materialism, it is impossible to declare that practices of knowing is exclusively a human practice. It is not just because we include non-human components into our practices, but also because knowing requires that one aspect of the world make itself understandable to the other (Barad, 2003). Hence, because of the multi-directional and recursive nature of the complex causal relationships at issue, the various interacting components of an open system have the capacity to spontaneously develop collective features or patterns (Urry, 2005). In this sense, ‘onto-epistemology’, the study of ways of knowing in being, is perhaps a better approach to consider the kinds of comprehensions required to understand the significance of particular intra-actions (Barad, 2003).

In terms of the body, according to new materialism, “body is constituted as effects of material practices and relations” (Moser, 2003, p. 86). On the one hand, this means that body is not given and that it is difficult to determine where, for example, body starts and stops. On the other hand, it indicates that subjectivity is entanglements that are made through material practices and relations rather than innate intellectual capacities or a socially constructed identity in a natural, individualized body (Moser, 2003). Through intra-action with something or someone outside, the body transforms into another and becomes something else. The body is therefore an assemblage of various parts and objects that become entangled with other productions and are involved in a variety of flows and breaks. It doesn’t have a stable identity, but instead shifts, changes, and is cleaned away from one particular position into a variety of flows (Grosz, 1995) that, consequently, creates possibilities for non-hierarchical, fragmental, temporal, repetitive, and ongoing material, spatial and time structures to emerge.

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